

The Influence of Audio Visual Media on Student Learning Outcomes Sub Theme 1 Learning Weather Conditions 1 Grade III SD 097320 Serapuh T.A 2023/2024

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine the influence of audio visual media on student learning outcomes, Sub Theme 1 Weather Conditions Learning 1 Class III SD Negeri 097320 Serapuh T.A 2023/2024, the method in this research is a quantitative experimental type method whose research design is Pre-experimental type one pretest-posttest group. Conducted in October 2023, the population in this research was class III students at SD Negeri 097320 Serapuh for the 2023/2024 academic year with two research variables: the dependent variable (x) in the form of learning outcomes, and the independent variable (y) in the form of Audio Visual media, media Audio-visual is a combination of audio media and visual media or usually called hearing-view media which makes the presentation of learning theme content more complete. The data collection technique is a test technique with validity testing. Test results using the Normality Test, Homogeneity Test and N-Gain Test with the help of the SPSS version 23 programs, based on the calculation results, the average value (mean) was 66.5405. Which means that there is an influence of the use of the Audio Visual media model on student learning outcomes Sub Theme 1 Weather Conditions Learning 1 Class III State Elementary School 097320 Serapuh T.A 2023/2024.

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the determining factors for success in efforts to increase quality human resources and shape the human spirit to become oneself as a unique person. Education can function as guidance/help given to children by adults deliberately so that children become adults, can develop knowledge, improve the quality of life and human dignity by utilizing all the potential they have without having to depend on other people. (Bukhari, 2020). In Republic of Indonesia Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System article 3 states "National education functions to develop abilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in order to educate people who have faith and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and a democratic and responsible citizen"

Thematic learning is learning that is packaged in the form of themes based on the content of several subjects that are combined. A theme is a forum or vehicle for introducing various material concepts to students as a whole. Thematic learning is believed to be an effective learning approach because it is able to accommodate and touch students emotionally, physically and academically in an integrated manner in the classroom or school environment. The model used in the learning process. Student characteristics are very important for teachers to know because they will be used as a reference in formulating the desired teaching strategy (Nevi Septiani, et al: 2020).

In this day and age, students' interest and enthusiasm in the world of education is very reduced, and they do not have interest in educational fields so that it has a big impact on the learning outcomes obtained by students who often do not reach the standard grades for the subjects, especially in research areas at SDN. 097320 Serapuh, Gunung Malela District, Simalungun Regency, North Sumatra Province. Based on observations made by researchers while conducting Field Experience Practices (PPL), researchers can see that there are still many students who experience difficulties in digesting thematic learning.

Efforts are made to increase student interest and learning outcomes by utilizing existing technology to make work or human activities in general easier. Technology is also able to contribute to helping develop the world of education. Therefore, teachers must be able to choose the right media in learning by using the audio-visual method. What is the definition of audio visual? According to Wina Sanjaya (2014: 118), a type of media that apart from containing sound elements also contains image elements that can be seen, such as video recordings, various sizes of film, sound slides and so on.

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Especially in today's developments, learning media should be the main pillar in making it easier for educators to convey information about learning to students easily and creatively. In some areas the role of Audio-visual learning media is not really involved in helping provide learning information, especially

in the world of education, such as in the Serapuh area which is densely packed with SDN 097320 Serapuh, Serapuh District, Simalungun Regency, North Sumatra Province where the role of Audio-visual media has not been utilized in the process. teaching and learning, so researchers are interested in introducing audio visual learning to students.

Student learning outcomes are still classified as low or minimal, and there are still many students who get scores that do not reach the KKM, learning in Sub Theme 1 Class III weather conditions. There are 60% of students who have not completed the KKM (Indonesian), 40% of students who have not completed (Mathematics) 30% of students who have not completed (SBdP) 36%. From this explanation it can be concluded that there are still many students whose grades do not reach the KKM. The completeness of learning outcomes is a factor that influences low learning outcomes that originate from within the student which includes interests, talents, motivation, health, intelligence. Many students tend to just pay attention to the teacher without giving feedback or responding so that when the teacher asks, everyone just stays silent.

Based on the background that has been described, the researcher was interested in researching and thinking about solutions to the problems faced, so the researcher took the title "The Influence of Audio Visual Media on Student Learning Outcomes Sub Theme 1 Weather Conditions Learning 1 class III SD Negeri 097320 Serapuh."

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The process of learning activities, especially thematic (integrated) teaching and learning activities, using the right media will give a special impression to students. Learning using the right media will motivate students to increase their enthusiasm for learning thematic learning.

In an effort to improve the quality of lessons, researchers are trying to use audio visual media to improve student learning outcomes, so that students are more motivated and can more easily master the material they are studying and will not make students feel bored because students will also be more active in learning.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

This type of research is quantitative research with experimental research methods. According to Syafrida Hafni Sahir (2021:13) Quantitative Methods are research with tools for processing data using statistics, therefore the data obtained and the results obtained are in the form of numbers. According to Yusuf (2014: 78) experimental research is an investigation that is designed in such a way. So that the phenomenon or event can be isolated from other drivers.

This research design is pre-experimental design using one group pretest-posttest design. This research design only involved one class by giving a pretest and posttest.

Subjek	Pretest	Treatment	Posttest
Kelas III SDN 097320 Serapuh	O ₁	X	O ₂

Figure 2. One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design

Information:

O₁ = Pretest value before treatment

X = Treatment given

O₂ = Posttest value after treatment

Population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population referred to by the researcher is an object/subject that has certain characteristics that have been determined by the researcher to be studied. The population in this study were class III students at SD Negeri 097320 Serapuh for the 2023/2024 academic year.

RESULTS

This research is a pre-experimental research using a one group pretest-posttest design conducted in Class III at SD Negeri 097320 Serapuh with a total of 25 students. The questions given when conducting research were validated first in class III at different schools, namely: at UPTD SD NEGERI 122395 Jln Sibatu-batu. with a total of 16 students. After validation of the questions was carried out, it was continued with conducting research in Class III at SD Negeri 097320 Serapuh. in Subtheme 1 "Weather Conditions", the first thing carried out in this research was giving a pretest to students so that they could find out the students' learning outcomes before the Audio Visual Media learning model (treatment) was carried out, then learning was carried out in subtheme 1 in learning using the learning model Audio Visual Media after learning is carried out and then a posttest is carried out to determine the learning outcomes of students after implementing the Audio Visual Media learning model.

Test instrument

1. Validity Test

Table 1. Validity Test

No Item	Pearson Correlation (R_{count})	R_{table}	Information
1	0,595754	0.396	Valid
2	0,641748	0.396	Valid
3	0,715979	0.396	Valid
4	0,606488	0.396	Valid
5	0,650157	0.396	Valid
6	0,649523	0.396	Valid
7	0,620833	0.396	Valid
8	0,41762	0.396	Valid
9	0,7069	0.396	Valid
10	0,509012	0.396	Valid
11	0,428131	0.396	Valid
12	0,494488	0.396	Valid
13	0,463042	0.396	Valid
14	0,513569	0.396	Valid
15	0,595522	0.396	Valid
16	0,576992	0.396	Valid
17	0,404299	0.396	Valid
18	0,472593	0.396	Valid
19	0,453736	0.396	Valid
20	0,4224	0.396	Valid

2. Normality Test

The data normality test is used to see whether the students' pre-test and post-test data are normally distributed. In this research, the Kolmogorov-Simirnov and Shaprio-Wilk tests were used using the SPSS-26 application. The basis for decision making is that if the significance level is >0.05 , then the student data values are normally distributed and if on the contrary the significance level is <0.05 then the student data values are not normal. From the normality results using the SPSS-26 application, the following results were obtained:

Table 2. Normality Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		28
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000

	Std. Deviation	5.47821990
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.127
	Positive	.127
	Negative	-.089
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.672
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.757

Based on the results of the normality test carried out, it is known that the significance value is $0.757 > 0.05$. Then it can be concluded that the residual values are normally distributed.

3. Homogeneity Test

The homogeneity test is used to test whether the two samples have the same characteristics or not. The results of the homogeneity test of post-test and pre-test scores are as follows.

Table 3. Homogeneity Test

$r_{count} =$	Largest variance/smallest variance
$r_{count} =$	1
$r_{table} =$	2,010634758 $r_{count} < r_{table}$ 1 < 201

Based on the homogeneity test results table above, it can be seen that the calculated $r < r_{table}$ is $1 < 201$ so it can be stated that the two sample groups have homogeneous variance.

4. N-Gain Test

In this study, a sample test was used to assess the influence of the Audio Visual media model on the learning outcomes of class III students in (subtheme 1, the influence of Audio Visual media), which can be seen from the following table:

Table 4. N-Gain Test

Class		Statistic		Std. Error
n_gain_percent	Experiment	Mean		66,5405
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	61,8901
			Upper Bound	71,1908
		5% Trimmed Mean		66,2653
		Median		63,6364
		Variance		126,922

		Std. Deviation	11,26597	
		Minimum	46,15	
		Maximum	91,67	
		Range	45,51	
		Interquartile Range	13,56	
		Skewness	,571	,464
		Kurtosis	,172	,902

From the table above it can be seen that the class average (mean) value is 66.5405. Which means that there is an influence of the use of the Audio Visual media model on student learning outcomes.

DISCUSSION

This research is a pre-experimental research using a one group pretest-posttest design conducted in Class III at SD Negeri 097320 Serapuh with a total of 25 students. The questions given when conducting research were validated first in class III at different schools, namely: at UPTD SD NEGERI 122395 Jln Sibatu-batu. with a total of 16 students. After validation of the questions was carried out, it was continued with conducting research in Class III at SD Negeri 097320 Serapuh. in Subtheme 1 "Weather Conditions", the first thing carried out in this research was giving a pretest to students so that they could find out the students' learning outcomes before the Audio Visual Media learning model (treatment) was carried out, then learning was carried out in subtheme 1 in learning using the learning model Audio Visual Media after learning is carried out and then a posttest is carried out to determine the learning outcomes of students after implementing the Audio Visual Media learning model.

This research was carried out at SD Negeri 097320 Serapuh in class III with a total of 25 students as the research sample. In this research, the scores of two variables are the results of a test consisting of 20 multiple choice questions which were administered to 25 students as a research sample. These two variables are student learning outcomes before treatment (pretest) and learning outcomes after treatment with audio-visual media learning (posttest).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the discussion in this chapter, the researcher provides the opportunity to formulate the problem and hypothesis as well as the research results obtained. then a discussion of all research activities carried out regarding the influence of the use of Audio Visual media on the Learning Outcomes of Class III Students at SD Negeri 097320 Serapuh first learning was carried out.

1. a. At SD Negeri 097320 Serapuh in Subtheme 1 learning 1, the average score for the pretest was relatively low.
2. b. By using Audio Visual media in Subtheme 1 lesson 1, a very significant development of learning outcomes was obtained, where giving the posttest resulted in relatively high learning outcomes.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

So further lessons that can be given to make it better in the future are:

1. To educators, especially teachers at SD Negeri 097320 Serapuh, so that we can use Audio Visual media as a model for learning in schools.
2. Researchers are aware of the lack of student learning outcomes regarding learning in the world of education so that its implementation still requires attention and supervision by teachers in schools.
3. It is hoped that future researchers will be able to develop this research by studying Audio Visual media in more detail and depth.
4. To the students of SD Negeri 097320 Serapuh to be more enthusiastic about learning and train themselves for each new learning model in order to create a comfortable and interesting learning atmosphere.

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